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**ATTITUDE OF GRADUATE STUDENTS TOWARDS VALUE-ORIENTED
EDUCATION IN KURUKSHETRA UNIVERSITY**

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Abstract:

Present study was undertaken to the attitude of graduate students towards value- orientated education in Kurukshetra University. For this investigation, descriptive study was conducted, for this purpose 120 respondent of graduate students were selected randomly from Kurukshetra University. The aim of this study was to compare the attitude of arts, commerce and science graduate students towards value-oriented education. A self made scale for measuring the attitude of under graduate students towards value- oriented education. Investigator found that there is no significant difference between the attitude of art, commerce and science graduate students towards value-oriented education.

Key words; Attitude, Value-Oriented Education

INTRODUCTION:

Education]does not mean merely acquiring knowledge, gathering facts, but it means self-improvement, to see the significance of life as whole. It is an urgent and immediate need to foster character and discipline among generation. The youth is in a more complex. The whole world is convinced beyond doubt that the only effective antidote to this concerns is value based system of education because the right knowledge is supposed to cure all ills of life. Value-Oriented Education refers to the variety of educational interventions — ‘Curricular and to the proposed to deal with general deterioration in values in all walks of life. Through value-oriented

education we would like to develop the social, moral, aesthetic and spiritual sides of a person which are often ignored within formal education. Value education teaches us to preserve what is good and worth-while in what we have inherited from our culture. It helps us to accept and respect the attitude and behaviour of those who differ from us. Value does not mean value imposition. The purpose of value oriented education is to fight obscurantism, religious fanaticism and violence and promote and nurture critical thinking, reasoning and build up a human approach to life” NCERT Director J.S. Rajput quoted as saying in a statement.

VALUE-ORIENTED EDUCATION: SOME BASIC ISSUES: A Major issue relates to what specific values should schools transmit. Instead of providing a long list of values, it is meaningful to highlight the type of values to be promoted in our school system. It is very difficult to identify a particular set of values as number of values overlap under more than one type. The values frequently mentioned for inclusion in school education are: **a) Personal Values, b) Social Values, c) Moral Values, d) Spiritual Values**

Significant of this study:

The present day situation is that we are living in the world of science and technology are advancing very fast while on the other hand the society is facing problem of alcohol, drug abuse, stress, mental illness, crime etc. Westernization, Modernization, Privatization have led to emergence of the market economy resulting in cut throat competition, sharp decline of values, consumerism and corruption. Today, what is being done is to educate heads and hands and not the hearts. Therefore, value education is very much important because the children of today are the adults of tomorrow and whatever they are taught as young student is what will mould them. Thus, due to great significance of values in our lives investigator decided to study the attitude of graduate students towards value-oriented education.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Sewell (2003) found in his study that eighty-six percent indicated that character education was strongly needed. Overwhelmingly, teachers agreed that character education can be (Strongly Agree & Agree = 98.9%) and should be (Strongly Agree & Agree = 87.1%) integrated in the family and consumer sciences curriculum. The teachers responding to this survey indicated that they had extensive knowledge

of the character traits (Strongly Agree & Agree = 95.4%) and how to teach (Strongly Agree & Agree = 88.2) character traits. The last statement in this section asked teachers to indicate if they thought that all students should be required to take character education as a separate class taught by family and consumer sciences teachers. Thirty percent indicated that they were undecided.

Butt & Shams (2013) This study explored the student teacher attitudes towards research. The sample consisted of 194 participants from two public universities of Pakistan and it was taken by using census sampling technique. The Attitude towards Research scale was used for data collection. The scale was consisted of 30 items which were divided into five factors. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-test and ANOVA. The results showed that student teachers have a negative attitude towards research. Significant difference was found in the attitudes with respect to the type of program and prior areas of specialization. The paper demonstrates a clear need for focus on research into student teacher attitudes towards research. Low student teacher attitudes have negative impact on the pupils.

Rama& Reddy (2014) The main purpose of this study was to examine the attitude of final year degree students towards value education in Chittoor town. In this study, random sampling method was adopted. The participants of the study were 320 final year degree students of Chittoor town, Andhra Pradesh, India. The tool used in the study for data collection was a 70 item questionnaire developed by the researchers by reviewing a number of books, news paper articles dealing with value education. The findings of the study revealed that entire sample of students had a positive but significant difference in their attitude towards value education. Different other variables like socio-economic status, religion, caste etc. can be included.

Reddy& Reddy(2015) The main objective of this study is to study the influence of management, type of family on the attitude of B.Ed. students towards value oriented education. Value oriented education questionnaire developed by Suneetha, P (2008) was adopted. A sample of 320 B.Ed. students representing. In this study 't' – test and ANOVA ('F' - test) were employed for analysis of the data. There is significant influence of management at 0.01 level and type of family at 0.05 level of significance on the attitude of B.Ed. students towards value oriented education.

Chauhan(2015) The present paper throws light on the values of trained graduate secondary school teachers of Patiala district of Punjab as Social, Political, Religious, Economical, Aesthetic Economic and Theoretical value education. A sample of 100 male and female trained graduate secondary school teachers was taken for the present research. The main objective of the present paper is to find out

various types of values existing among male and female trained graduate teachers of secondary schools. The present paper also suggested some ways to promote values among the students in educational institutions.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1. To investigate the attitude of graduate students towards value-oriented education.
2. To compare the attitude of male and female graduate students towards value-oriented education.
3. To compare the attitude of arts and science graduate students towards value-oriented education.
4. To compare the attitude of science and commerce graduate students towards value-oriented education.
5. To compare the attitude of arts and commerce graduate students towards value-oriented education.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of male and female graduate students towards value-oriented education.
2. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of science and arts graduate students towards value-oriented education.
3. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of science and commerce graduate students towards value-oriented education.
4. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of arts and commerce graduate students towards value-oriented education.

RESEARCH METHOD:

This research is survey method was considered to be most appropriate for undertaking this investigation. The major purpose of survey method in research is to describe the problem phenomenon.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE:

The present investigation consists of a random sample of 120 students of university college of Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.

TOOL USED:

Researcher used self-made scale for assessing the attitude of under graduate students towards value- oriented education. For the selection of items for attitude scale the investigator had to go through books, journal and other materials related to the concept, “Value-oriented education” from the available materials. Researcher rests of 40 items were selected for Value-oriented education attitude scale. Out of 40 items 6 items (19,20,21,25,28,30.) were negative and rest items were positive. A final draft had 40 items with five points scale i.e. Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and strongly disagree. This scale consists of 7 dimension viz. Cultural, Educational, Moral, Personal, Religious, Social, Spiritual .

PROCEDURE OF DATA COLLECTION:

After selecting the tools, the investigator visited to university colleges of Kurukshetra on the basis of sample details. Permission for administration attitude scale was taken from the principal of college. The time for administration of the test were fixed. They were also informed that the test results and their responses will be kept confidential. After completion the answer sheets were collected from all the students.

STATISTICAL TOOLS USED:

Descriptive statistics like Mean and Standard Deviations & t-test was used to find out the significance of difference were used to study the nature of the distribution.

Analysis Of Data And Result

Attitude Of Male And Female Students Towards Value- Oriented Education

Groups	N	M	S.D.	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male Students	60	151.5	11.5	3.11	Significant at 0.01 level.
Female Students	60	144.8	13.1		

This table shows that the mean attitude score of male and female graduate students towards value-oriented education are 151.5 and 144.8 respectively where as standard deviations of the same group are 11.5 and 13.1. The t-value is found to be 3.11 which is significant at 0.01 level. It indicates that two groups differ significantly on their attitude towards value-oriented education. Hence, the earlier stated hypothesis, "There exists no significant difference in the attitude of male and female college student towards value-oriented education." is rejected.

ATTITUDE OF SCIENCE AND ARTS STUDENTS TOWARDS VALUE- ORIENTED EDUCATION

Groups	N	M	S.D.	't' Value	Level of Significance
Science students	30	147.8	11.1	1.59	Not significant at 0.05 level
Arts students	30	153.8	17.4		

This table shows that the average of attitude score of Science and Arts students towards value-oriented education are 147.8 and 153.8 respectively where as the standard deviations of the same groups are 11.1 and 17.4. The t-value is found to be 1.59 which is not significant at 0.05

levels of significance. It indicates that two groups not differ significantly on their attitude towards value-oriented education. Hence, the earlier stated hypothesis, “There exists no significant difference in the attitude of Science and Arts-students towards value-oriented education.” is accepted.

**ATTITUDE OF SCIENCE AND COMMRECE STUDENTS TOWARDS VALUE -
ORIENTED EDUCATION**

Groups	N	M	S.D.	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
Science Students	30	147.8	11.1	3.02	Significant at 0.01 level
Commerce Students	30	137.2	115.7		

It showed that average of attitude scores of Science and Commerce students towards value-oriented education are 147.8 and 137.2 respectively where as standard deviations of the same groups are 11.1 and 15.7. The t-value is found to be 3.02 which is significant at 0.01 level. It indicates that science and commerce groups differ significantly on their attitude towards value-oriented education. Hence, the earlier stated hypothesis, “There exists no significant difference in the attitude of Science and Commerce college student towards value-oriented education.” is rejected.

**ATTITUDE OF ARTS STUDENTS AND COMMERCE STUDENTS TOWARDS
VALUE-ORIENTED EDUCATION**

Groups	N	M	S.D.	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
Arts Students	30	153.8	17.4	3.88	Significant

Commerce Students	30	137.2	15.7		at 0.01 level
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This table showed that average of attitude scores of Arts and Commerce students towards value-oriented education are 153.8 and 137.2 respectively where as standard deviations of the same group are 17.4 and 15.7. The t-value is found to be 3.88 which are significant at 0.01 levels. It indicates that art and commerce groups differ significantly on their attitude towards value-oriented education. Hence, the earlier stated hypothesis, “There exists no significant difference in the attitude of Arts Students and Commerce college student towards value-oriented education.” is rejected.

Conclusion:

- It was hypothesized that there is no significant difference between the attitude of male and female graduate students towards value-oriented education. After analysis of data it was found that data does not support the assumption and reject the hypothesis. It depicts that male student have favorable attitude towards value-oriented education in compare to female students.
- It was hypothesized that there exists no significant difference between attitude of science and Arts students towards value-oriented education. After analysis of data, it was found that the attitudes of arts and commerce graduate students don't differ significantly. So the hypothesis was accepted.
- It was hypothesized that there exists no significant difference between Science and Commerce students towards value-oriented education. After analysis of data it was found that the attitudes of Science and Commerce students differ significantly, with Science

students having more favorable attitude value oriented education than their Commerce counterparts.

- It was hypothesized that there exists no significant difference between Arts and Commerce students towards value-oriented education. After analysis of data it was found that the attitudes between Arts and commerce students differ significantly, with Arts students having more favorable attitude towards value oriented education than Commerce students. Therefore the above stated hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion: From this study and the findings, it was found that total sample of graduate students were having positive attitude towards value education but a significant difference was found in the attitudes of subgroups.

Educational Implication:

- By introducing value-oriented education in our environment sportsmanship, team-spirit and leadership qualities of the students can be developed.
- Stories, illustrations and events mainly from Indian nation and its literature from various religious that included in value-oriented education leads to national integration.
- Value education will eliminate obscurantism, religious fanaticism, violence, superstitions and fatalism among the students.
- Only value based education system can nurture the basic values of humanism, democracy, socialism and secularism.
- Thus, value-oriented education has significant contribution to the society in general and for the students in particular.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDY:

- Study can be conducted on teachers working in colleges and schools

- A study can be conducted to probe into the deterioration of values in modern period and their suggestion can be gathered from the people who belong to the different state of society.
- An investigation can be carried out on a large sample belonging to different states in our country.

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